

TO STUDY THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND DRUG–EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY OF RANOLAZINE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A STABLE PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

In situ gel drug delivery systems have attracted considerable interest in recent years due to their ability to provide sustained drug release, enhanced bioavailability, prolonged gastric residence time, and improved patient compliance. The present study was aimed at performing preformulation characterization and drug–excipient compatibility evaluation of Ranolazine for its application in gastro-retentive in situ gel formulation. Preformulation studies including organoleptic evaluation, pH determination, melting point analysis, and solubility studies were conducted to assess the physicochemical properties of the drug. Ranolazine exhibited a near-neutral pH, indicating good aqueous stability. The melting point analysis confirmed the crystalline nature and purity of the drug sample. Solubility studies revealed that Ranolazine was freely soluble in methanol, soluble in ethanol, sparingly soluble in acetone, and slightly soluble in distilled water, highlighting the need for

formulation strategies to improve aqueous solubility.

Ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometric analysis was performed to determine the maximum wavelength of absorption (λ_{max}), which was found to be 272 nm in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. Calibration curves prepared in 0.1 N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 demonstrated good linearity with high correlation coefficients, confirming the reliability and accuracy of the developed analytical method for quantitative estimation. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to characterize the functional groups of Ranolazine and to investigate its compatibility with selected excipients such as pectin and HPMC K4M. The FTIR spectra of drug–excipient physical mixtures showed no significant peak shifting, disappearance, or formation of new peaks, indicating the absence of chemical interactions. Overall, the findings of this study confirmed the chemical stability and compatibility of Ranolazine with selected excipients, thereby supporting its suitability for further development of gastro-retentive in situ gel drug delivery systems.

KEYWORDS: Ranolazine, In situ gel, Preformulation studies, Drug–excipient compatibility, FTIR spectroscopy, UV spectrophotometry, Gastro-retentive drug delivery, Sustained release.

In-situ gels

The development of in-situ gelation systems has received considerable attention in the last few years. In situ gel delivery systems are capable of continuous drug release while maintaining a constant drug concentration in the blood plasma. In- situ gel systems are liquid at room temperature but converted into gels when they come into contact with physiological body fluids. Gel formation depends on many factors, such as temperature modulation, pH changes, presence of ions, ultraviolet radiation, electrical sensitivity and enzymes that release the active substance in-situ gels are suspensions or solutions that, after reaching a certain point, undergo gelation.^[1] Physical and chemical changes including body fluid exposure or UV exposure external triggers ion concentration, pH, temperature, availability of specific molecules or ions and others, a steady state plasma drug concentration profile can be generated from in situ gels using sustained drug release. So that the drug is effectively absorbed from the gel and improves bioavailability Compared to conventional drug formulations, in-situ gel delivery systems have potential advantages such as simple manufacturing process, ease of administration, low frequency of administration, improved compliance and patient comfort. In-situ gels are liquid drugs that can be easily applied to sites of absorption. A firm gel forms at the site of drug absorption (Figure 1.1).^[2] It is able to

prolong the release time of the drug. Natural and synthetic polymers can be used to form gels in situ. In situ gel formation is induced by one or a combination of different stimuli, such as pH-sensitive, temperature-sensitive and ionic cross-linking polymers. Recent advances in peritoneal route and liquid in situ oral gels allowed us to exploit changes in physical specificity in different regions of the GI tract to enhance drug absorption and improve bioavailability. Polymer solutions known as gels in situ, depending on the temperature of the application site, ionic strength or pH and the formation of a gel system. The mechanism of this formation process uses polymeric materials in response to external stimulation, therefore, under physiological conditions, the polymer undergoes a reversible phase transition from of a solution to a gel by changing its dispersion or conformational state emphasizing the advantages of fluids and gels, these gels vary widely in their application prospects for drug delivery such as oral administration, ocular administration, nasal systems and implants.^[3]

Figure 1.1: In-situ gels.

There are three categories of in situ gels based on their phase change efficiency, namely heat-triggered systems, pH-triggered systems and ionic force-triggered systems. PH-triggered gelation is another method of in situ gel formation based on the physiological stimulation of any polymer that is sensitive to changes in pH, has an acidic or basic group that either accepts or releases protons in response to the surrounding pH the term polyelectrolytes refers to polymers with a large amount of ionized groups, a slightly acidic anionic group in the polymer can increase the external pH and cause the hydrogel to swell, while when the polymer contains a weakly basic group, the cationic external pH decreases when cations such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and Na^{+} are present in this system ionic activation of the gelling system changes in ionic strength cause the liquid injected to gel this gelling system undergoes a liquid-to-gel phase transition as the ionic strength increases.^[4]

The in-situ gel formation mechanism can be divided into chemical and physical mechanisms. Physical mechanisms are stimulated by temperature, electric fields, and light. Chemical mechanism is stimulated by pH change and ion activation. The in-situ gel formation mechanism by temperature, pH, and ions may vary depending on the type of gel system used. Here in situ, some common mechanisms associated with these factors are.

pH-triggered in situ gel

The slightly acidic or basic groups that form the backbone of pH-sensitive polymers respond to changes in pH by releasing or accepting protons, free hydrophobic electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding interactions leading to inter diffusion and conformational changes in the polymer at a specific pH that cause the polymer to expand upon increasing pH. Polymer forms hydrogen bonds that lead to the formation of hydrogel networks. The in situ gelation process triggered by pH is shown in Figure 1.2.

In a pH-sensitive gelation system, the gel develops immediately when bio stimuli are introduced to it, since ionized groups are present on the polymer surface, these systems can exhibit sudden changes in ion affinity and water solubility over certain pH ranges.^[5]

Figure 1.2: In situ gel process activated by pH triggering.

pH-sensitive polymers some polymers have pH-sensitive properties where they change from a liquid to a gel form when the pH changes, for example polymers such as polyacrylate alginate or methyl cellulose can form a gel when the pH of the solution reaches a certain threshold change in pH can cause changes in bonds between polymers leading to the formation of a gel.^[6]

Environmental pH changes some in situ gels can form gels in response to environmental pH

changes, for example in the acidic environment of the stomach in situ drug gels containing acidic polymers experience a drop in pH and form a gel that allows the drug contained in them to be released.

In-Situ Temperature Triggered Gel

Temperature triggered upon exposure to an ambient temperature of 20- 25°C the temperature-induced in situ gelling polymers become liquid and at 35 to 37°C physiological temperature begins to form a gel mechanism is shown in Figure 1.3 the optimal temperature-sensitive in situ gelling solution must have a phase change temp. higher than the ambient temperature of 25°C.^[7] The development of hydrophobic regions and the formation of a hydrogel network from the liquid, both of which are influenced by temperature, accelerate the breakdown of the polymer chain. Liquid-to-gel transformation in the in-situ gelation mechanism is caused by exposure to a thermal trigger, which is considered an external stimulus.

Figure 1.3: In situ gel gelling mechanism activated by temperature.

Solution to gel transition some polymers can undergo solution to gel transition when temperature changes occur at a certain temperature polymer in liquid solution form a stable gel network, for example poly isopropyl acryl amide acid is one of the most commonly used temperature-sensitive polymers in situ gel systems can form gel at temperatures above a certain gelation temperature called the critical point of the solution.^[8]

Ion activated in situ gel

In this type of gelation system, a liquid to gel phase change occurs due to the effect of increasing ionic strength gels occur in tear fluid due to complexation with polyvalent cations

such as Ca^{2+} , the ion-activated in situ gelation mechanism is shown in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4: In situ gel gelling mechanism by ionic active polymers.

Formation of ionic bonds some polymers can form gels by forming ionic bonds with certain ions, for example gelatin is a polymer often used in in-situ gel systems in which calcium ions are used to form stable cross-links between gelatin chains to form a strong gel.^[9] Controlling viscosity using ions adding certain ions to a polymer solution can affect the viscosity of the solution and aid in gel formation, for example adding sodium or calcium ions to an alginate solution can increase the viscosity and create a stable alginate.

Combination approaches

Combinational approaches involve the integration of multiple mechanisms or stimuli sensitivities in in-situ gels to achieve prolonged gastric residence and controlled drug release. These combined approaches offer increased flexibility and versatility in drug delivery systems. Some common combination approaches include.

a) Dual sensitivity to pH and temperature

Dual pH and temperature sensitive formulations use polymers that respond to changes in both pH and temperature. Gelation behaviour can be fine-tuned to occur at specific pH levels and temperature ranges. This allows better control over drug release and ensures targeted delivery to specific areas of the gastrointestinal tract.

b) Triple responsive ion activated, thermosensitive, pH triggering: In this approach, gelling agents sensitive to specific ions are combined with thermosensitive polymers. Gelation can be triggered by either ion activation or temperature change, providing additional control over drug release kinetics.

Figure 1.5: Combination approaches of two or more stimuli responsive systems.

The essential features of in situ gel formation technology are high viscosity and high gel strength and the mixture should have the right viscosity to be directly administered as a solution that would quickly turn into a gel.

One of the main advantages of in situ gel formation technology is that it enables controlled drug delivery. In situ gel can also increase the bioavailability of the drug and extend the sustained release in the application, resulting in maximum efficacy. Sustained release is an approach to drug formulation that allows the drug to be delivered over time while maintaining a stable and therapeutic level of the drug in the body, creating drug delivery systems that gradually release the drug over time, often resulting in increased patient compliance and reduced dosing frequency of extended-release formulations may improve therapeutic efficacy by maintaining drug concentrations in the therapeutic range for a longer period of time, which may lead to improved therapeutic efficacy.

The drug contact time of sustained release formulations is generally longer than that of immediate release formulations. One of the main goals of sustained-release drugs is to provide a gradual and sustained release of the drug over a longer period of time, as such sustained-release drugs are designed to maintain therapeutic levels of the drug in the body for a longer period of time than immediate-release dosage forms. Moreover, it helps preserve the

quality of the drug and makes it more stable. In studies of how drugs are released using models, it is very important to understand how they are released, different models have been used to explain the release behaviour of a drug from gels in situ in simulated gastric fluid, such as Zero-order kinetics, First-order kinetics model Higuchi and Korsmeyer-peppas models.^[10-14]

Advantages of in situ gels

Figure 1.6: Advantages of in situ gels.

Disadvantages of Floating In-Situ Gel Systems

1. Dependence on Physiological Conditions
2. Risk of Incomplete or Delayed Gelation
3. Limited Mechanical Strength of the Gel Matrix
4. Potential Gastrointestinal Irritation
5. Limited Suitability for High-Dose Drugs

Preformulation Studies

Preformulation testing is the first and most essential step in the rational development of pharmaceutical dosage forms. It involves the systematic evaluation of the physicochemical properties of a drug substance that may influence its formulation, stability, bioavailability, and therapeutic performance. The primary objective of preformulation studies is to optimize drug delivery by generating critical information needed to design an efficacious, stable, and safe

dosage form.

Preformulation studies help define the nature of the drug substance and provide a scientific framework for formulation development. Important parameters such as solubility, pKa, partition coefficient, particle size, polymorphism, and stability are assessed to understand how the drug will behave during processing, storage, and administration. This information guides the selection of appropriate dosage forms, excipients, and manufacturing methods, thereby reducing formulation-related risks in later stages of development.

Identification studies are carried out as part of preformulation testing to confirm the identity and purity of the drug sample. Techniques such as melting point determination, infrared spectroscopy, and thermal analysis are commonly used to ensure that the obtained drug substance meets the required standards. Accurate identification is crucial before proceeding further in formulation development.

Additionally, drug–excipient compatibility studies are performed to evaluate possible interactions between the drug and commonly used excipients. These studies help identify incompatibilities that may affect the stability, efficacy, or safety of the formulation. The results obtained from preformulation studies serve as a foundation for the development of a robust and reliable dosage form with optimal therapeutic performance.

Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties of the drug substance, including appearance, colour, and physical nature, were evaluated by visual inspection. A small quantity of Ranolazine powder was examined under normal lighting conditions to assess its colour, texture, and general appearance. This evaluation helps in the preliminary identification of the drug and provides useful information regarding its purity and uniformity.

Determination of pH

The pH of Ranolazine was determined to assess its ionization behavior and stability in aqueous medium. A 5% w/v drug solution was prepared by dissolving Ranolazine in distilled water. The pH of the solution was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. Prior to measurement, the pH meter was standardized using buffer solutions of known pH. The electrode was then immersed in the drug solution, and the pH reading was recorded once a stable value was obtained. The pH value provides important information related to drug

solubility, stability, and compatibility with excipients, which is crucial for formulation development.

Melting Point Determination

The melting point of Ranolazine was determined using the Thiele's tube method, which is a commonly employed technique for the identification and purity assessment of solid drug substances. Melting point determination provides valuable information regarding the crystalline nature of the drug and helps in detecting the presence of impurities, as pure compounds exhibit a sharp and characteristic melting point range.

In this method, a clean and dry glass capillary tube was sealed at one end by gentle heating. A small quantity of finely powdered Ranolazine was then introduced into the open end of the capillary tube and gently tapped to allow the drug to settle at the sealed end, forming a compact column of uniform height. The filled capillary tube was securely tied to a calibrated thermometer in such a way that the drug sample remained close to the thermometer bulb to ensure accurate temperature measurement.

The thermometer with the attached capillary tube was placed inside a Thiele's tube containing liquid paraffin, which served as the heating medium. The Thiele's tube was heated gradually using a controlled flame, allowing uniform circulation of the liquid paraffin to maintain an even temperature rise. Care was taken to heat the system slowly, especially near the expected melting point, to obtain precise observations.

The melting point of Ranolazine was determined by noting the temperature at which the drug particles just began to melt (onset of melting) and the temperature at which the entire sample was completely liquefied (completion of melting).^[15]

Determination of drug solubility in various solvent

The solubility of Ranolazine was determined in different solvents to understand its dissolution behavior and to support the selection of suitable solvents for formulation development. Commonly used solvents such as distilled water, methanol, ethanol, and acetone were selected for the study, as they represent aqueous and organic media with varying polarities.

An excess amount of Ranolazine was added separately to each solvent in clean, stoppered test tubes. The mixtures were shaken intermittently and allowed to stand at room temperature for

a sufficient period to attain equilibrium. After equilibration, the solutions were visually observed to determine the extent of solubility, and undissolved drug particles, if any, were noted.

Based on the observations, the solubility of Ranolazine in each solvent was categorized as freely soluble, soluble, sparingly soluble, or practically insoluble. The solubility data obtained from this study is essential for predicting the drug's dissolution behavior, selecting appropriate formulation techniques, and improving bioavailability in the development of an effective dosage form.^[16]

Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy Determination of λ Max in 0.1 N HCl

The ultraviolet (UV) spectrum of Ranolazine was recorded using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Jasco V-730) to determine its maximum wavelength of absorption (λ_{max}), which is essential for drug identification and quantitative analysis. UV spectrophotometry is widely used in preformulation studies due to its simplicity, sensitivity, and suitability for routine analysis. Accurately weighed 10 mg of Ranolazine was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in a sufficient quantity of 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. The volume was then made up to the mark with the same solvent to obtain a stock solution of concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The solution was shaken thoroughly to ensure complete dissolution of the drug. From the stock solution, 1 ml aliquot was withdrawn and transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up to the mark using acetone, yielding a working solution with a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. This dilution was selected to ensure that the absorbance values remained within the linear range of the instrument. The prepared solution was scanned over a wavelength range of 200–400 nm against an appropriate blank using the UV-visible spectrophotometer. The obtained spectrum was recorded, and the wavelength at which maximum absorbance occurred (λ_{max}) was noted. The λ_{max} value obtained confirms the identity of Ranolazine and serves as a basis for further analytical and formulation studies.

Preparation of Calibration Curve by using 0.1 N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 A stock solution of Ranolazine with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was prepared separately using 0.1 N hydrochloric acid and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as solvents. An accurately weighed quantity of the drug was dissolved in each solvent and the volume was made up to the required mark to obtain the stock solutions. These solvents were selected to simulate gastric and intestinal pH conditions and to study the drug's absorbance behavior in different media.

From the prepared stock solutions, a series of standard dilutions were made to obtain concentrations in the range of 40–160 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in the respective solvents. The dilutions were prepared using the same solvent to maintain consistency and accuracy in the analysis. The absorbance of each prepared solution was measured at 272 nm, which corresponds to the λ_{max} of Ranolazine, using a UV–visible spectrophotometer. The respective solvents were used as blank solutions to eliminate background interference. The absorbance values obtained were used to construct calibration curves, which demonstrate the linear relationship between concentration and absorbance in accordance with Beer–Lambert’s law. These calibration curves are essential for the quantitative estimation of Ranolazine in further formulation and dissolution studies.^[17-18]

Characterization of Sample by Fourier Transform Infra- Red Spectra

The compatibility of Ranolazine with selected gelling agents and other excipients was evaluated using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectral analysis. This study was carried out to investigate any possible physical or chemical interactions between the drug and excipients such as Pectin, HPMC K4M, Calcium chloride, and Sodium citrate, which could affect the stability, efficacy, or performance of the formulation.

Individual samples of Ranolazine and the selected excipients, as well as their physical mixtures, were subjected to FTIR analysis. The samples were prepared by the potassium bromide (KBr) disc method, wherein a small quantity of each sample was thoroughly mixed with dry KBr and compressed into a transparent disc under hydraulic pressure. This method ensures uniform dispersion of the sample and accurate spectral interpretation.

The infrared absorption spectrum of Ranolazine was recorded over a wave number range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using a Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (Jasco FT/IR-4600). The characteristic peaks corresponding to functional groups of Ranolazine were identified and compared with those obtained from the spectra of drug–excipient mixtures. The absence of significant shifts, disappearance, or formation of new peaks in the FTIR spectra indicated that Ranolazine was compatible with the selected gelling agents and excipients. Thus, the FTIR study confirmed that no chemical interaction occurred between the drug and excipients, supporting their suitability for use in the formulation development.

Drug Excipients Compatibility Study

Drug–excipient compatibility studies were carried out using Fourier Transform Infrared

(FTIR) spectroscopy (Jasco FT/IR-4600) to evaluate possible interactions between Ranolazine and the selected excipients. This analysis helps in identifying any chemical incompatibilities that may affect the stability, safety, or efficacy of the formulation during processing and storage. For the study, Ranolazine was mixed with each excipient in an equal proportion to form physical mixtures. A small quantity of each mixture was prepared for FTIR analysis using a KBr cell method. The prepared mixture was carefully placed on the sample cell, which was then fitted into the sample holder of the FTIR instrument.

The infrared spectra of the drug–excipient mixtures were scanned over a frequency range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The obtained spectra were recorded and analyzed for the presence of characteristic peaks of Ranolazine and compared with those of the pure drug. Particular attention was given to any shift, disappearance, or formation of new peaks, which could indicate potential interactions. The spectral analysis revealed that the characteristic functional group peaks of Ranolazine were retained in the presence of excipients without significant changes. This indicated the absence of chemical interactions between the drug and excipients, confirming their compatibility and suitability for use in the formulation development.^[19-20]

Preformulation Studies

Organoleptic Analysis: Ranolazine was evaluated for its organoleptic properties like appearance, colour, odour and nature by visual inspection.

Table 1.1: Organoleptic Analysis.

Sr. No.	Properties	Description
1	Appearance / Nature	Fine Crystalline
2	Colour	White
3	Odour	Characteristic

Determination of pH

The pH of a 5% w/v Ranolazine solution prepared in distilled water was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter under controlled laboratory conditions. Prior to measurement, the pH meter was standardized using appropriate buffer solutions to ensure accuracy and reproducibility of the readings. The measured pH of the Ranolazine solution was found to be 6.8 ± 0.02 , indicating a near-neutral environment. pH is a critical physicochemical parameter that significantly influences the solubility, chemical stability, and bioavailability of pharmaceutical compounds. Additionally, it plays a vital role in determining the compatibility of a drug with excipients, dosage forms, and physiological fluids. Deviations from an optimal

pH range may lead to drug degradation, precipitation, or reduced therapeutic efficacy. Therefore, the determination of pH is an essential preliminary step in the formulation development process.

Ranolazine is a weakly basic drug, and its dissolution behavior in aqueous media is governed by its ionization characteristics. The observed pH value of 6.8 suggests that, despite its basic nature, Ranolazine exhibits a slightly acidic to neutral pH when dissolved in distilled water. This behavior may be attributed to partial protonation of the drug molecule as well as the influence of dissolved atmospheric carbon dioxide in water, which can lead to mild acidification. The near-neutral pH also reflects the intrinsic ionic nature of Ranolazine in aqueous solution. A pH value close to neutrality is advantageous from both stability and safety perspectives. Extreme acidic or alkaline conditions can accelerate hydrolytic or oxidative degradation pathways, potentially compromising the chemical integrity of the drug. The observed pH indicates that Ranolazine is unlikely to undergo significant pH-induced degradation under these conditions, thereby supporting its chemical stability in aqueous formulations. Furthermore, a near-neutral pH is desirable for oral dosage forms, as it minimizes the risk of gastrointestinal irritation and enhances patient compliance.

The obtained pH value is consistent with previously reported literature values for Ranolazine solutions, thereby validating the reliability and accuracy of the experimental procedure. This consistency also confirms the suitability of distilled water as a solvent for preliminary formulation studies involving Ranolazine.

Melting Point

The melting range of a compound is an important physicochemical parameter that provides valuable information regarding its identity and purity. A pure crystalline substance typically exhibits a sharp and narrow melting range, whereas the presence of impurities generally results in a broader melting range and a depression in melting temperature. Therefore, determination of the melting range is commonly employed as a preliminary qualitative test for assessing the purity of pharmaceutical substances.

In the present study, the melting range of Ranolazine was determined using the Thiele's tube method, a conventional and reliable technique for melting point analysis. The sample was carefully packed into a capillary tube and heated gradually, and the temperature at which the drug began to melt and completely liquefied was recorded.

The melting range of Ranolazine was observed to be 123°C, which falls well within the reported standard range of 120–124°C. The narrow melting range obtained indicates the crystalline nature of the drug and suggests the absence of significant impurities. This close agreement with the official or literature-reported melting range confirms the identity of the drug and demonstrates the high purity of the supplied sample.

The results of the melting range determination support the suitability of Ranolazine for further pharmaceutical formulation and analytical studies. The absence of melting point depression or broadening further indicates that the drug is chemically stable and has not undergone degradation during storage or handling.

Determination of Solubility of Drug in Various Solvents

The solubility of Ranolazine was evaluated in different solvents including distilled water, methanol, ethanol, and acetone. The observations are summarized below:

Table 1.2: Solubility of Drug in Various Solvents.

Solvent	Solubility of Ranolazine
Distilled Water	Slightly soluble
Methanol	Freely soluble
Ethanol	Soluble
Acetone	Sparingly soluble

Solubility is a critical physicochemical parameter that significantly influences the absorption, bioavailability, and therapeutic efficacy of a pharmaceutical drug. Understanding the solubility behavior of a drug in various solvents is essential for rational formulation design, selection of appropriate solvent systems, and development of reliable analytical methods. In the present study, the solubility of Ranolazine was evaluated in different solvents to assess its solvent-dependent dissolution behavior.

The solubility study revealed that Ranolazine exhibits variable solubility in different solvents, which can be attributed to its inherent physicochemical properties. Ranolazine is a moderately lipophilic compound with weakly basic characteristics, and its solubility is strongly influenced by solvent polarity and hydrogen-bonding capacity. Among the solvents tested, Ranolazine showed the highest solubility in methanol, indicating a strong interaction with polar protic solvents capable of forming hydrogen bonds with the functional groups present in the drug molecule.

Ethanol also demonstrated good solubilizing capacity for Ranolazine, although to a slightly lesser extent than methanol. This difference may be attributed to the lower polarity of ethanol compared to methanol, which marginally reduces its ability to solvate the drug molecules. In contrast, the solubility of Ranolazine in acetone was found to be limited, suggesting that polar aprotic solvents are less effective in dissolving the drug due to the absence of hydrogen-donating capability.

In distilled water, Ranolazine was only slightly soluble, highlighting a potential challenge in the development of aqueous-based formulations. Poor aqueous solubility is a common limitation for many lipophilic and weakly basic drugs and can result in reduced dissolution rate and bioavailability, particularly in oral dosage forms. This observation indicates the need for solubility enhancement strategies such as the use of co-solvents, pH adjustment, cyclodextrin inclusion complexes, solid dispersions, or nanoparticulate drug delivery systems to improve aqueous solubility and dissolution characteristics.

The observed solubility profile provides valuable guidance for both formulation development and analytical method selection. Solvents such as methanol and ethanol are suitable for preparing stock solutions for spectroscopic and chromatographic analysis due to their high solubilizing capacity. Conversely, formulations intended for aqueous environments may require optimization through suitable solubility enhancement techniques to ensure effective drug delivery and therapeutic performance.

In conclusion, Ranolazine exhibits pronounced solvent-dependent solubility, being freely soluble in methanol, soluble in ethanol, sparingly soluble in acetone, and slightly soluble in water. These findings are of considerable importance in guiding formulation strategies, selecting appropriate solvent systems, and ensuring adequate drug dissolution, ultimately contributing to improved bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy.

Ultraviolet-Visible Spectroscopy Determination of λ Max in 0.1 N HCl

The UV–visible absorption spectrum of Ranolazine was recorded using a stock solution of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ prepared in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. The spectrum exhibited a well-defined maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) at 272 nm, which is in close agreement with previously reported literature values, thereby confirming the reliability of the analytical method and the authenticity of the drug sample (Figure 1.13).

Determination of the λ_{max} is a fundamental step in pharmaceutical analysis, as it identifies the wavelength at which the drug exhibits maximum absorption of ultraviolet radiation. This wavelength is subsequently employed for quantitative estimation of the drug using UV spectrophotometry to ensure optimal sensitivity and accuracy. In the case of Ranolazine, the observed λ_{max} at 272 nm is attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ electronic transitions, which are characteristic of aromatic rings and conjugated systems present within the molecular structure of the drug.

The selection of 0.1 N HCl as the solvent plays a crucial role in this analysis. Ranolazine, being a weakly basic compound, exhibits enhanced solubility in acidic media due to protonation, ensuring complete dissolution and uniform molecular dispersion. Furthermore, the acidic medium simulates the gastric environment, making the analysis particularly relevant for oral formulation and dissolution studies.

The consistency of the observed λ_{max} with literature-reported values serves as an indicator of the purity of the Ranolazine sample and validates the accuracy and reproducibility of the experimental procedure. The sharp and distinct absorption peak also suggests the absence of interfering impurities or degradation products that could otherwise alter the spectral profile.

In conclusion, the UV-visible spectroscopic analysis confirms that Ranolazine exhibits a characteristic absorption maximum at 272 nm in 0.1 N HCl. This wavelength is suitable for subsequent quantitative analytical studies and provides a reliable basis for method development, validation, and routine quality control of Ranolazine-containing formulations.

Figure 1.13: UV- Visible Spectrum of Ranolazine in 0.1 N HCl.

Calibration Curve by using 0.1 N HCl and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 Calibration curve of Ranolazine in 0.1 N HCL

A calibration curve for Ranolazine was developed using 0.1 N hydrochloric acid as the solvent to establish a reliable relationship between drug concentration and absorbance for quantitative analysis. Standard solutions were prepared in the concentration range of 40– 160 µg/mL, and the absorbance of each solution was measured at the previously determined λ_{max} of 272 nm using a UV–visible spectrophotometer. All measurements were performed in triplicate, and the mean absorbance values were calculated to minimize experimental variability (Table 1.3).

The calibration plot of absorbance versus concentration demonstrated a linear relationship across the studied concentration range, indicating consistent adherence to Beer–Lambert’s law. The linear regression analysis yielded a high correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 0.9961$), confirming excellent linearity and suitability of the method for quantitative estimation of Ranolazine within this range.

The low standard deviation observed among the triplicate measurements reflects the good precision and reproducibility of the analytical procedure. The positive slope of the regression equation indicates a direct proportional increase in absorbance with increasing Ranolazine concentration, thereby validating the selection of 272 nm as an appropriate analytical wavelength.

The small negative intercept observed in the regression equation may be attributed to minor instrumental noise or baseline correction effects, which are commonly encountered in UV spectrophotometric analysis and do not significantly influence the accuracy or reliability of the method.

The use of 0.1 N HCl as the solvent provides a stable acidic environment that ensures complete solubilization of Ranolazine, a weakly basic drug, thereby enabling consistent and accurate absorbance measurements. This solvent system also enhances method robustness by minimizing variability associated with incomplete dissolution or precipitation.

In conclusion, the calibration curve of Ranolazine in 0.1 N HCl exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 40–160 µg/mL, with a correlation coefficient of 0.9961. The results confirm that the developed UV spectrophotometric method is accurate, precise, and

reproducible, making it suitable for routine quantitative analysis of Ranolazine in bulk drug substances as well as pharmaceutical formulations during further analytical and

Figure 1.14: Calibration curve of Ranolazine in 0.1 N HCL.

Table 1.3: Calibration curve of Ranolazine in 0.1 N HCL.

Sr. No.	Concentration in µg/ml	Absorbance			
		I	II	III	Mean
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	40	0.3007	0.3265	0.3215	0.3162
3	60	0.4303	0.4555	0.4587	0.4481
4	80	0.5864	0.6129	0.6196	0.6063
5	100	0.687	0.6837	0.6875	0.6860
6	120	0.8076	0.8349	0.8426	0.8283
7	140	0.9536	0.9852	0.9863	0.9750
8	160	1.0611	1.0643	1.0975	1.0743
Equation of line ($y = mx + c$)				$y = 0.0066x - 0.041$	
Coefficient of correlation (r^2)				0.9961	

*All values are expressed as Mean \pm SD, n =3

Calibration curve of Ranolazine in Phosphate buffer 6.8

A calibration curve for Ranolazine was constructed in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 using standard solutions prepared in the concentration range of 40–160 ppm. The absorbance of each solution was measured at the previously established analytical wavelength of 272 nm, and the corresponding absorbance values are summarized in Table 1.4. The calibration plot of absorbance versus concentration exhibited a consistent and proportional increase in absorbance with increasing drug concentration, demonstrating good linearity across the selected range.

Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 is widely used to simulate the intestinal physiological environment, making it particularly relevant for the analytical evaluation of orally administered drugs such as Ranolazine. The linear relationship observed between concentration and absorbance confirms that Ranolazine follows Beer–Lambert’s law in this buffer system within the studied concentration range.

A gradual and uniform increase in absorbance values was observed, ranging from 0.2597 at 40 ppm to 1.0666 at 160 ppm, indicating effective solubilization of Ranolazine and stable absorbance behavior in phosphate buffer pH 6.8. This consistent trend suggests that the buffer system provides a suitable medium for UV spectrophotometric estimation of Ranolazine, particularly for applications involving dissolution testing, drug release studies, and *in vitro* performance evaluation.

The absence of irregular fluctuations or deviations in absorbance further reflects the precision and reproducibility of the analytical procedure, as well as the compatibility of Ranolazine with the buffer medium. These results support the reliability of the developed calibration curve for routine quantitative analysis.

In conclusion, the calibration curve of Ranolazine in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 demonstrated good linearity over the concentration range of 40–160 ppm, confirming the suitability of this buffer system as an analytical medium for UV spectrophotometric estimation of Ranolazine. This method is particularly useful for dissolution and intestinal release studies and provides a reliable foundation for further formulation development and *in vitro* evaluation.

Figure 1.15: Calibration curve of Ranolazine in Phosphate buffer 6.8.

Table 1.4: Calibration curve of Ranolazine in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8.

Sr. No.	Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	40	0.259667
3	60	0.3927
4	80	0.5374
5	100	0.687967
6	120	0.822467
7	140	0.97533
8	160	1.066633

*All values are expressed as Mean \pm SD, n =3

Drug Excipients Compatibility Study FTIR of Ranolazine (Pure Drug).

Figure 1.16: FTIR Spectrum of Ranolazine.

Table 1.5: Reported and observed FTIR Frequencies of a Ranolazine (Pure Drug).

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Observed Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	Reported Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
1	N-H	3375.78	3400-3200
2	N=O	1495.53	1550-1350
3	C-O	1245.79	1300-1000
4	C-H	799.35	900-690
5	C=N	1641.13	1690-1641
6	O-H	2351.77	3400-2400

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed as a qualitative analytical technique to confirm the identity of Ranolazine and to characterize its functional groups prior to formulation development. FTIR analysis is widely used in pharmaceutical preformulation

studies as it provides valuable information regarding the chemical structure, functional group integrity, and purity of drug substances. The FTIR spectrum of pure Ranolazine was recorded and the observed absorption bands were compared with reported literature values to assess structural conformity.

The FTIR spectrum of Ranolazine exhibited several well-defined and characteristic absorption bands, all of which closely corresponded with the reported reference ranges, thereby confirming the chemical identity and structural integrity of the drug. A prominent absorption band observed at 3375.78 cm^{-1} was attributed to N–H stretching vibrations, which falls within the reported range of $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak confirms the presence of secondary amine functionality in the Ranolazine molecule. The slight shift from the upper limit of the reported range may be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding and solid-state molecular interactions, which are commonly observed in crystalline pharmaceutical compounds.

The presence of the nitro (N=O) functional group, a key structural and pharmacologically relevant moiety in Ranolazine, was confirmed by a distinct absorption band at 1495.53 cm^{-1} . This peak lies within the reported range of $1550\text{--}1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and corresponds to asymmetric stretching vibrations of the nitro group. The clear appearance of this band indicates the preservation of this functional group without chemical alteration or degradation.

An absorption band at 1245.79 cm^{-1} was assigned to C–O stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of $1300\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak confirms the presence of ether or alcohol-related functional groups within the Ranolazine structure and supports the integrity of its molecular framework. Additionally, a distinct band observed at 799.35 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–H bending vibrations, typically associated with aromatic or substituted alkyl groups. This value lies within the reported range of $900\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$, further supporting the aromatic nature of the drug molecule.

The C=N stretching vibration, a critical structural feature of Ranolazine, was observed at 1641.13 cm^{-1} , which closely matches the lower limit of the reported range ($1690\text{--}1641\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The sharpness and intensity of this peak indicate the presence of a stable imine linkage and confirm the molecular integrity of the drug substance.

In addition, a weak but distinct absorption band at 2351.77 cm^{-1} was assigned to O–H

stretching vibrations, corresponding to the broad reported range of 3400–2400 cm^{-1} . This band may arise due to hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl groups or the presence of trace moisture associated with the crystalline form of Ranolazine. Such minor absorption is commonly observed in solid-state FTIR spectra and does not indicate chemical impurity.

Compatibility Study of Drug and Polymer

The mixture of Ranolazine and excipients were recorded to check interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR of Ranolazine–Pectin Physical Mixture

Figure 1.17: FTIR Spectra of mixture of Ranolazine–Pectin Physical Mixture.

Table 1.6: Reported and observed FTIR Frequencies of a Ranolazine–Pectin Physical Mixture.

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Observed Frequencies (cm^{-1})	Reported Frequencies (cm^{-1})
1	C-H	796.57	900-690
2	C=C	1634.38	1662-1626
3	C-O	1248.68	1300-1000
4	N-H	3276.47	3500-3100

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to investigate the potential chemical interactions between Ranolazine and pectin, a natural polysaccharide polymer commonly used in pharmaceutical formulations. Compatibility studies are a crucial component of preformulation development, as chemical interactions between the drug and excipients may compromise drug stability, efficacy, and performance. FTIR spectroscopy is a well-established technique for identifying such interactions through the evaluation of functional group integrity and peak shifting behavior.

In the present study, the FTIR spectrum of the physical mixture of Ranolazine and pectin was recorded and compared with the characteristic absorption bands of the pure drug and polymer as reported in the literature. The spectrum of the physical mixture exhibited well-defined and distinct absorption bands corresponding to the functional groups of both Ranolazine and pectin, indicating that both components retained their chemical identities in the mixture.

A characteristic absorption band observed at 796.57 cm^{-1} was attributed to C–H bending vibrations, typically associated with aromatic or substituted alkyl groups present in the Ranolazine molecule. This absorption falls within the reported range of $900\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and appeared without any significant shift, broadening, or reduction in intensity. The preservation of this peak suggests that the aromatic framework of Ranolazine remains structurally intact in the presence of pectin and is not involved in any chemical interaction. An absorption peak at 1634.38 cm^{-1} was assigned to C=C stretching vibrations, which lie within the reported range of $1662\text{--}1626\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak may arise from the aromatic moieties of Ranolazine and/or the glycosidic backbone of pectin. The retention of this peak at nearly the same wavenumber, without distortion or splitting, indicates the absence of chemical modifications such as conjugation, oxidation, or degradation of either component. This observation further confirms the chemical stability of Ranolazine when combined with pectin.

The C–O stretching vibration was observed at 1248.68 cm^{-1} , which lies well within the reported range of $1300\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band is characteristic of ether linkages and glycosidic bonds present in pectin, as well as C–O functional groups within the Ranolazine molecule. The appearance of this peak without disappearance, excessive broadening, or the emergence of additional peaks suggests that the polymeric structure of pectin remains preserved and that no chemical reactions such as esterification or covalent bonding occur between the drug and polymer.

A broad absorption band observed at 3276.47 cm^{-1} corresponds to N–H stretching vibrations, which falls within the reported range of $3500\text{--}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak confirms the presence of amine functionality of Ranolazine in the physical mixture. The slight broadening of this band may be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the amine groups of Ranolazine and the abundant hydroxyl groups of pectin. Such interactions are commonly observed in drug–polymer systems and are considered physical interactions, which can be beneficial for drug dispersion and matrix formation but do not indicate chemical incompatibility or instability.

Importantly, the FTIR spectrum of the Ranolazine–pectin physical mixture did not show any new peaks, significant peak shifting, or disappearance of characteristic absorption bands. The absence of these spectral changes indicates that no chemical interactions, degradation, or complex formation occurred between Ranolazine and pectin during mixing.

FTIR of Ranolazine–HPMC K4 M Physical Mixture

Figure 1.16: FTIR of Ranolazine + HPMC K4 M.

Table 1.7: Reported and observed FTIR Frequencies of a Ranolazine + HPMC K4M.

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Observed Frequencies (cm^{-1})	Reported Frequencies (cm^{-1})
1	C–O	1219.76	1350–1000
2	C–H	769.45	900–690
3	C=C	1634.38	1662–1626
4	O=C=O	2400.94	2400–2000
5	N–H	3337.21	3400–3200

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to evaluate the potential chemical interactions between Ranolazine and HPMC K4M, a widely used hydrophilic matrix-forming polymer in controlled-release pharmaceutical formulations. Compatibility assessment between the drug and excipients is a critical step in preformulation studies, as chemical incompatibility may lead to drug instability, altered release behavior, or reduced therapeutic efficacy. FTIR spectroscopy serves as an effective tool for detecting such interactions by identifying changes in characteristic functional group absorption bands.

In the present study, the FTIR spectrum of the physical mixture of Ranolazine and HPMC K4M was recorded and compared with the spectra of the individual components as reported in the literature. The resulting spectrum exhibited well-defined absorption bands corresponding to the characteristic functional groups of both Ranolazine and HPMC K4M, indicating that the chemical identities of the drug and polymer were preserved upon mixing.

A prominent absorption band observed at 1219.76 cm^{-1} was assigned to C–O stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of $1350\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band is characteristic of the ether linkages present in the cellulose backbone of HPMC K4M, as well as the C–O functional groups of Ranolazine. The retention of this peak at nearly the same wavenumber, without noticeable shifting or intensity changes, suggests that the polymeric structure of HPMC K4M remains chemically intact and that no covalent bonding or esterification occurred between the drug and the polymer.

A distinct absorption band at 769.45 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–H bending vibrations, which lie within the reported range of $900\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This peak is associated with aromatic or substituted alkyl groups present in the Ranolazine molecule. The presence of this peak at a similar position in the physical mixture indicates that the aromatic framework of Ranolazine remains unchanged and is not involved in any chemical interaction with HPMC K4M.

The C=C stretching vibration, characteristic of unsaturated or aromatic moieties of Ranolazine, was observed at 1634.38 cm^{-1} , falling within the reported range of $1662\text{--}1626\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The absence of peak shifting, broadening, or disappearance in this region indicates that no chemical modification such as conjugation, oxidation, or degradation of the drug occurred upon interaction with the polymer.

An additional absorption band at 2400.94 cm^{-1} was attributed to $\text{O}=\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations, which lie within the reported range of $2400\text{--}2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This band is commonly associated with atmospheric carbon dioxide or trace carbonate-related vibrations and is frequently observed as an artifact in FTIR spectra. Its presence does not indicate chemical incompatibility between Ranolazine and HPMC K4M and is considered environmentally or instrumentally derived rather than formulation-related.

A broad absorption band observed at 3337.21 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\text{N}\text{--}\text{H}$ stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of $3400\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, confirming the presence of amine functionality of Ranolazine in the physical mixture. The slight broadening of this band may be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the $\text{N}\text{--}\text{H}$ groups of Ranolazine and the hydroxyl (--OH) groups of HPMC K4M. Such hydrogen bonding interactions are physical in nature and are commonly observed in drug–polymer systems. Importantly, these interactions do not indicate chemical incompatibility and may even contribute positively to matrix formation and drug release modulation.

FTIR of Optimized Formulation (F8)

Figure 1.19: FTIR Spectra of a Solution of Ranolazine and Mixture.

Table 1.8: Reported and observed FTIR Frequencies of a solution of Ranolazine and mixture.

Sr. No.	Functional Group	Observed Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	Reported Frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
1	C-O	1219.76	1350-1000
2	C=C	1636.3	1662-1626
3	N=O	1548.60	1550-1350
4	O=C=O	2407.69	2400-2000
5	N-H	3289.96	3400-3200
6	C-X	678.82	785-540
7	C-H	770.43	900-690

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was employed to evaluate the chemical stability of Ranolazine in solution and to assess the presence of any potential drug–excipient or drug–solvent interactions in the final formulation. FTIR analysis is a widely accepted technique for monitoring changes in chemical structure, functional group integrity, and molecular interactions that may arise during formulation processing. The observed FTIR spectra of the Ranolazine solution and the final mixture were compared with reported literature frequencies to confirm structural preservation.

The FTIR spectrum of Ranolazine in solution and in the final mixture exhibited all characteristic absorption bands corresponding to its functional groups, indicating that the chemical structure of the drug remained intact throughout solution preparation and formulation processing. Importantly, no additional peaks, peak disappearance, or major shifts in wavenumber were observed, suggesting the absence of chemical degradation or incompatibility.

An absorption band observed at 1219.76 cm⁻¹ was attributed to C–O stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of 1350–1000 cm⁻¹. This band corresponds to ether or alcohol-related functional groups present in the Ranolazine molecule. The retention of this peak at a consistent position indicates that the C–O linkages remained chemically stable, with no evidence of cleavage, esterification, or oxidative degradation during formulation. A prominent absorption band at 1636.30 cm⁻¹ corresponds to C=C stretching vibrations, which lie within the reported range of 1662–1626 cm⁻¹. This peak is associated with the aromatic and unsaturated moieties of Ranolazine that contribute to its conjugated system. The persistence of this band without noticeable shifting confirms that the aromatic framework and

conjugation of the drug were preserved, indicating structural stability in both solution and final formulation.

The presence of the nitro (N=O) functional group, a key structural and pharmacologically relevant moiety of Ranolazine, was confirmed by a distinct absorption band at 1548.60 cm^{-1} , which falls within the reported range of 1550–1350 cm^{-1} . The clear appearance of this peak suggests that the nitro group remained chemically unaltered and did not undergo reduction, hydrolysis, or other chemical transformations during processing.

An additional absorption band at 2407.69 cm^{-1} corresponds to O=C=O stretching vibrations, which lie within the reported range of 2400–2000 cm^{-1} . This band is commonly attributed to atmospheric carbon dioxide or trace carbonate-related vibrations and is frequently observed as an artifact in FTIR spectra. Its presence does not indicate chemical incompatibility or instability and is considered unrelated to the drug or formulation components.

A broad absorption band observed at 3289.96 cm^{-1} was assigned to N–H stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of 3400–3200 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of amine functionality in Ranolazine. Slight broadening of this band may be attributed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the amine groups of the drug and solvent molecules or excipients in the formulation. Such hydrogen bonding interactions are physical and reversible in nature and do not indicate chemical instability or degradation. The absorption band at 678.82 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–X stretching vibrations, which fall within the reported range of 785–540 cm^{-1} . This band is associated with halogenated moieties present in the Ranolazine structure. The retention of this peak confirms the stability of halogen functional groups, indicating that no dehalogenation or related chemical reactions occurred during formulation.

Additionally, an absorption band at 770.43 cm^{-1} was attributed to C–H bending vibrations, which lie within the reported range of 900–690 cm^{-1} . This peak further supports the preservation of aromatic and alkyl groups within the Ranolazine molecule and reinforces the overall structural stability of the drug.

REFERENCES

1. Sharma S, Sarkar G, Srestha B, Chattopadhyay D, Bhowmik M. In-Situ Fast Gelling Formulation For Oral Sustained Drug Delivery Of Paracetamol To Dysphagic Patients.

- Int J Biol Macromol. 2019, Aug 1; 134: 864-868. Doi: 10.1016/J.Ijbiomac.2019.05.092. Epub 2019 May 16. Pmid: 31102679.
2. Pashikanti, Shailaja & B., Jyothsna. (2019). Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating In Situ Gel Of Ciprofloxacin. International Journal Of Applied Pharmaceutics. 11. 198. 10.22159/Ijap.2019v11i1.28603.
 3. Mahmoud Db, Shukr Mh, Elmeshad An. Gastroretentive Cosolvent-Based In Situ Gel As A Promising Approach For Simultaneous Extended Delivery And Enhanced Bioavailability Of Mitiglinide Calcium. J Pharm Sci., 2019 Feb; 108(2): 897-906. Doi: 10.1016/J.Xphs.2018.09.020. Epub 2018 Sep 26. Pmid: 30267785.
 4. Mercy, M. Formulation And Evaluation Of Gastroretentive Floating In-Situ Gel Of Minocycline Hcl.
 5. S M, Sindhoor & Priya, Sneha & Maxwell, Amala. (2018). Formulation And Evaluation Of Novel In Situ Gel Of Lafutidine For Gastro Retentive Drug Delivery. Asian Journal Of Pharmaceutical And Clinical Research, 11: 88. 10.22159/Ajpcr.2018.V11i8.25582.
 6. Dilesh J. Singhavi, Rashmi S. Pundkar, Shagufta Khan, Famotidine Microspheres Reconstituted With Floating In Situ Gel For Stomach-Specific Delivery: Preparation And Characterization, Journal Of Drug Delivery Science And Technology, 2017; 41: 251-259, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.Jddst.2017.07.017>.
 7. Patel, Ravi & Gandhi, Jaimini & Shah, Pranav. (2017). Floating In-Situ Gelling System For Stomach Specific Oral Drug Delivery Of Valacyclovir. International Research Journal Of Pharmacy, 8: 25-33. 10.7897/2230-8407.089154.
 8. Maheswaran, A. & Padmavathy, J. & Nandhini, V. & Saravanan, Dhanavel & Angel, P. (2016). Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating Oral In Situ Gel Of Diltiazem Hydrochloride. International Journal Of Applied Pharmaceutics, 9: 50. 10.22159/Ijap.2017v9i1.15914.
 9. Kumar, K. & Swathi, M. & Srinivas, Lankalapalli & Shaik, Naseeb. Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating In Situ Gelling System Of Losartan Potassium. Der Pharmacia Lettre., 2015; 7: 98-112.
 10. Alhamdany, Anas. (2014). Development And In Vitro/In Vivo Evaluation Of Floating In Situ Gelling Oral Liquid Extended Release Formulation Of Furosemide. Original Article. <https://doi.org/10.20510/UKjpb/2/15/91114>
 11. Maharjan, Reshma & Subedi, G. Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating In Situ Gel Of Ranitidine Using Natural Polymers. International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2014; 6: 205-209.

12. Rao, Monica & Shelar, S.U. & Yunusi, A. Controlled Release Floating Oral In Situ Gel Of Itopride Hydrochloride Using Ph Sensitive Polymer. *International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2014; 6: 338-343.
13. Thomas, Lena. Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating Oral In-Situ Gel Of Metronidazole. *International Journal Of Pharmacy And Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2014; 6: 265-269.
14. Shabaraya, A. & Ashwini, T. & Vineetha, K.. (2023). Formulation And Evaluation Of Gastroretentive In Situ Gelling System Of Ketoprofen. *European Pharmaceutical Journal*. 70. 10.2478/Afpuc-2023-0018.
15. Dina B. Mahmoud, Marwa H. Shukr, Aliaa N. Elmeshad, Gastroretentive Cosolvent-Based In Situ Gel As A Promising Approach For Simultaneous Extended Delivery And Enhanced Bioavailability Of Mitiglinide Calcium, *Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2019; 108(2): 897-906.
16. J, A. N., A. L. Y, And A. B. "Development And Evaluation Of In Situ Gelling Gastroretentive Formulations Of Meloxicam". *Universal Journal Of Pharmaceutical Research*, May 2017; 2(3) Doi:10.22270/Ujpr.V2i3.R3.
17. V.Phani Deepthi, Et. Al. "Formulation And Evaluation Of Floating In-Situ Gel Of Clopidogrel." *Iosr Journal Of Pharmacy And Biological Sciences (Iosr-Jpbs)*, (2022); 17(6): 26-42.
18. Siraj Ns, Vrushabha Gj And Khan Gj: Design, Development And Evaluation Of Gastric Floating In-Situ Gel Of Piroxicam. *Int J Pharm Sci. & Res.*, 2020; 11(7): 3409-16. Doi: 10.13040/Ijpsr.0975-8232.11(7).3409-16.
19. R Jivani R, N Patel C, M Patel D, P Jivani N. Development Of A Novel Floating In-Situ Gelling System For Stomach Specific Drug Delivery Of The Narrow Absorption Window Drug Baclofen. *Iran J Pharm. Res.*, 2010; 9(4): 359-68. Pmid: 24381600; Pmcid: Pmc3870059.
20. El Nabarawi, M. A., Teaima, M. H., Abd El-Monem, R. A., El Nabarawy, N. A., & Gaber, D. A. Formulation, Release Characteristics, And Bioavailability Study Of Gastroretentive Floating Matrix Tablet And Floating Raft System Of Mebeverine Hcl. *Drug Design, Development And Therapy*, 2017; 11: 1081–1093. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S131936>